

Proper Orthogonal Decomposition based algorithm for reconstructing missing displacement measurements by Digital Image Correlation

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Abstract: Digital Image Correlation (DIC) is an optical, contactless technique used to obtain full-field displacement measurements. However, there are situations during testing when obstacles obscure the camera's field of view, preventing the capture of all displacements. This paper presents a method based on proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) that exploits the correlation between point displacements to reconstruct the missing data. The developed algorithm was tested in the context of elasto-plastic deformation of specimens, particularly in regions experiencing concentrated plastic deformation. The algorithm demonstrated exceptional performance, achieving an accuracy of well below 10% despite monitoring only 20% of the specimen during the experiment.

1. Introduction

Any specimen or structure exposed to an external action will deform, subjecting all of its material points to an arbitrary displacement. By knowing these displacements it is possible to assess local deformation in any point of the material, generally through quantification of strain tensor components. While local values of its components can be assessed through strain gauges, in number of scientific and engineering applications it is beneficiary to have a continuum description of deformation field over the structural component. To this purpose it is necessary to have full field displacement information which is commonly provided by Digital Image Correlation (DIC).

DIC is a widely used technique that offers a range of benefits, including ease of application, minimal environmental constraints, straightforward measurements with high accuracy, and the ability to capture large fields of displacement (e.g., see [1] and the references therein). Initially proposed by Peters and Ranson [2], the method employed a simple correlation algorithm to eliminate rigid-body motions and produce a displacement field directly associated with the specimen's deformation. Since its inception, the method has evolved, with several advanced algorithms developed to enhance both accuracy and efficiency (see e.g., [3-5]). Throughout few decades of its development it have seen successful applications in diverse scientific and engineering fields applied to different materials, ranging from polymers [6], metals

[7], rocks [14], with particularly interesting applications in structural health monitoring [9] and high temperature applications [10], [11].

While the method is theoretically capable of assessing the full displacement field over the entire monitored area, it requires that no physical obstacles be present between the camera and the sample during measurements. Additionally, optimal optical conditions must be ensured to provide sufficient contrast. The latter particularly becomes challenging when high temperature specimens are being monitored as the optical contrasts generally changes with changing of the specimen's surface temperature [7], [11], [12].

There are several situations in which, for various reasons, not all measurements can be captured with sufficient accuracy, or in some cases, cannot be captured at all. For instance, certain measurements may be obscured by elements of the experimental setup, or optical conditions might be suboptimal. In these scenarios, here proposed algorithm can prove highly beneficial, as it offers a robust mathematical framework for reconstructing missing data with exceptional accuracy. By leveraging advanced computational techniques, the algorithm is able to infer the displaced field in regions where direct measurements are unavailable, ensuring the integrity and completeness of the analysis. This ability to fill in gaps in the data makes the method particularly useful in complex experimental setups, where full visibility or ideal measurement conditions are not always achievable.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the developed algorithm for missing data reconstruction, based on Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD). In Section 3, we discuss the results of applying the algorithm to computer-generated data, designed to test the maximum achievable accuracy under idealized conditions. Section 4 summarizes the results obtained from real experimental data, including a brief description of the testing equipment used in the experiments. Finally, Section 5 offers comments, concluding remarks, and discusses potential avenues for future advancements and improvements in the method.

2. Reconstructing missing information by exploiting correlation

While displacement of different points in a structural component due to its deformation can assume arbitrary values, these values are not fully independent between each other. Considering that these points belong to the same structural component which, in general, preserves continuity

while being deformed, the displacements of different points are correlated to a large extent. By exploiting this correlation it is in principle possible to predict the displacement of some points just by knowing the displacement of certain other points within the same structure. A systematic way of exploiting this correlation is proposed in what follows by employing Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) technique. This method has wide applications in data analysis, under the name of Principal Component Analysis (PCA), employed to summarize the information content of a large datasets into a smaller set of uncorrelated variables [my book]. While it originates in statistics [14] throughout the years it have seen diverse applications in reduction of dimensionality applied in thermal analysis [15], in modeling turbulent flows [16], stress analysis in deformable bodies [17], fracture mechanics [18] and many others. The method systematically analyze data, and provides a set of orthogonal directions that can be used to project the original data into reduced sub-space, while at the same time preserving the accuracy. It also provides a systematic way to exploit the correlation between the data. The latter feature is of the relevance for the here presented application. In what follows the algorithm based on Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) will be employed to reconstruct the missing information.

2.1. Constructing POD basis of correlated data

The set of M correlated vectors in N -dimensional space can be stored in a so-called snapshot matrix \mathbf{U} . By performing POD analysis on this matrix it is possible to construct POD basis of it Φ . M vectors from the set are now expressed in this new coordinate frame (spanned by directions which represent columns of the matrix Φ) through the amplitude matrix \mathbf{A} . The relationship between snapshot matrix and its projection to the new reference frame is given by:

$$\mathbf{U} = \Phi \cdot \mathbf{A} \quad (1)$$

Details of how the POD basis of snapshot matrix can be constructed is given in Appendix 1.

It is worth mentioning that there is a mathematical proof (see e.g. [19]) that the POD basis Φ provides the best possible basis for constructing low order approximations of the given vectors in set (i.e. stored in the snapshot matrix \mathbf{U}). If, for example the goal is to provide a truncated approximation of all the vectors from the set by keeping just the first K components (with $K \ll N$), it is enough to keep the first K directions from the matrix Φ , to form $\bar{\Phi}$, with corresponding

truncated matrix of amplitudes $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$. N vectors are now represented by columns of matrix $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$ which collect K instead of N components. Vectors can be projected back to the original N dimensional space which now represent the approximation of original snapshot matrix, namely:

$$\mathbf{U} \approx \bar{\Phi} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{A}} \quad (2)$$

Proper orthogonal decomposition theory provides proof [19] that there cannot be any other basis where the error of such approximation will be smaller. The amount of error introduced by this approximation is related to the level of correlation between N vectors from the original set. In the case of fully correlated vectors (i.e. parallel vectors in their N -dimensional space), POD basis can be truncated to only one component, the vectors will be represented with only one scalar, and no loss of data will be introduced by this approximation (see e.g. [13]). In most other situations very good approximation is achieved if the first few (in general up to 10) directions from the POD basis are kept.

2.2.POD basis for numerically simulated data

Let the outputs of interest for a certain numerical model be N nodal displacements, collected in a vector \mathbf{u}_i . By performing M different simulations employing the same numerical model but changing e.g. boundary conditions, or some material parameters, M snapshots are generated that can be stored in an $N \times M$ snapshot matrix \mathbf{U} . POD analysis of this matrix, following the procedure described in Appendix 1, provides a new basis Φ to which snapshots can be projected. Considering that the snapshots are corresponding to the same numerical model, with only some boundary conditions and/or material parameters being changes, it is expected that they are closely correlated. Hence, a high accuracy approximation can be achieved by truncating the POD basis to first K (with $K \ll N$) directions to obtain $\bar{\Phi}$. Each of the snapshots is now represented with a single amplitude vector $\bar{\mathbf{a}}_i$, collecting K instead of N entries as was the original dimension of the system. While the approximated snapshot matrix can be obtained by a straightforward matrix multiplication given by equation (2), a single result of previously performed M simulations is approximated by:

$$\mathbf{u}_i \approx \bar{\Phi} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{a}}_i \quad (3)$$

Given the described construction of the snapshot matrix \mathbf{U} each row contains a nodal displacement for a particular degree of freedom of simulated structure, corresponding to different simulations. Hence, the value of the displacement that is placed in k^{th} position of the snapshot vector resulting from j^{th} simulation is approximated by:

$$u_j^k \approx \bar{\Phi}^k \cdot \bar{\mathbf{a}}_j \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\Phi}^k$ is k^{th} row of matrix $\bar{\Phi}$, and $\bar{\mathbf{a}}_j$ being j^{th} column of truncated amplitude matrix $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$.

2.3. Reconstructing missing data

Let us assume that for the given structure only for P points the displacements (i.e., entries to the snapshot vector) are known, with $P \ll N$. For ease of notation let us further assume that these points are placed from the first up to P^{th} position of the snapshot, namely:

$$\mathbf{u} = [u_1, u_2, \dots, u_P, u_{P+1}, \dots, u_N]^T \quad (5)$$

By assuming that for particular structure there already exists truncated POD basis $\bar{\Phi}$, approximated response related only the first P displacements is obtained by:

$$\mathbf{u}_q^{1 \div P} = \bar{\Phi}^{1 \div P} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{a}}_q \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{\Phi}^{1 \div P}$ is a $P \times K$ matrix that is constructed by taking the first P rows from $\bar{\Phi}$, considering that the known displacements are collected first within the snapshot matrix. Alternatively, it will take only rows corresponding to the known displacements. The vector of amplitudes $\bar{\mathbf{a}}_q$ is of the size $K \times 1$. When considered as a known quantity it can be also used to reconstruct the complete snapshot (and not only the part containing P quantities) by pre-multiplying it with complete truncated POD bases, namely:

$$\mathbf{u}_q = \bar{\Phi} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{a}}_q \quad (7)$$

Here considered problem of reconstructing the missing information can be formulated as follows. Let us assume that P quantities (i.e. measured displacements) are known values from the experiment. These quantities are collected in vector \mathbf{u}_{EXP}^P . The truncated POD basis $\bar{\Phi}$ for the complete region of interest is constructed first. Considering that the overall number of displacements within the considered region of interest is N and that the POD basis is truncated to first K directions, the truncated basis will be $N \times K$ matrix. From this basis the sub-basis $\bar{\Phi}^{1 \div P}$

containing rows corresponding to P quantities is extracted. For an arbitrary vector of amplitudes $\bar{\mathbf{a}}_C$ collecting K values, computed displacements are calculated by:

$$\mathbf{u}_C^P = \bar{\Phi}^{1+P} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{a}}_C \quad (8)$$

Now the goal is to find amplitude vector $\bar{\mathbf{a}}_C$ for which the difference between computed and experimental data is minimized. To this purpose the objective function is constructed as the L^2 norm of the vector of residuals:

$$\omega(\bar{\mathbf{a}}_C) = \|\mathbf{u}_C^P(\bar{\mathbf{a}}_C) - \mathbf{u}_{EXP}^P\|^{L^2} \quad (9)$$

This objective function is further minimized with respect to the unknown vector of amplitudes $\bar{\mathbf{a}}_C$. Upon solving the minimization problem the displacement of the whole region of interest are reconstructed as:

$$\mathbf{u}_C = \bar{\Phi} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{a}}_C \quad (10)$$

3. Computational validation

The computational exercises presented in what follows concern identification of displacement field over the wider specimen area by using only those from significantly smaller area. In all presented exercises the displacement field in the whole area is actually known and taken as reference point for comparative purposes.

3.1.Pseudo-experimental testing of hyper-elastic specimen

The first example discussed here involves a specimen with the geometry shown in Figure 1. To evaluate the developed procedure in a non-linear regime, where the correlation between displacements at different points is less pronounced, the material of the specimen is assumed to be rubber-like, undergoing large elastic deformations.

Figure 1: Specimen under consideration with area (dark grey) where displacements are considered to be known

A numerical model for this test is designed in ABAQUS [20], by attributing to the material hyper-elastic behavior modeled by Mooney-Rivlin elastic potential with the following constants: $C_{10}=0.139$, $C_{01}=0.02025$ and $D_1=0.254$, typical for polyphenylene vinylene polymers. These values were chosen to provide realistic numerical values for the constants, though it is clear that other materials could also be considered. Computational domain is discretized with 1147 nodes and 1075 quadrilateral elements with bi-linear, full integration of displacements over the element.

To exploit correlation between nodal displacements, 10 simulations under displacement control were performed by varying only boundary conditions. In all simulations bottom edge was kept fixed, while to the upper one the displacements equal to the following values was attributed: 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 22 and 30, in 10 simulations respectively. Alternatively, material parameter, or both could have been varied to contribute to a better exploring of the correlation under different conditions.

For verification purposes additional simulation was performed by attributing to the upper edge displacement of 19mm, hence the value not being used within the set of 10 simulations used to generate POD basis. From this simulation, only the displacements corresponding to the grey area depicted in figure 1 are taken as known, and formed the vector \mathbf{u}_{EXP}^P . By solving the

minimization problem with trust region algorithm, in the form as implemented in MATLAB [21], vector of amplitudes $\bar{\mathbf{a}}_C$ is found. These amplitudes, by employing the full POD basis, through the equation (10) is used to reconstruct the complete displacement field over the sample. Displacements are then compared against numerically generated by the same numerical model, from which only the set \mathbf{u}_{EXP}^P was taken, which are treated as references to compare to. The result is depicted in Figure 2. The color coded graph refers to the difference in displacements expressed in mm.

Figure 2: Difference in displacements expressed in mm, with zone from where displacements are considered to be known

From this purely numerical exercise conducting as at the proof of concept, it can be inferred that the propose algorithm performs exceptionally well. This straightforward exercise, which relied solely on numerical data, did not introduce any additional sources of error to assess the procedure's accuracy. As illustrated in the figure, the accuracy is impressive: in the region with the largest error (indicated by the yellow zone), the displacement difference is approximately 15 μm , while in the other regions, the difference is reduced to just a few

micrometers. Given the absolute displacement values (the upper edge is displaced by 19mm), the achieved error is well below one percent. From an engineering perspective, the two results can be considered practically identical.

Considered example is idealized and concerned only numerically generated to data. The idea behind this comparison was to test what is the expected maximum achievable accuracy, when no further errors is introduced by the interpolation of displacements from different point. The accuracy turns out to be exceptionally well, with the differences that are almost negligible. It is worth noting that fairly small number of simulations was used to construct the pod basis – specifically, only 10 simulations.

To further test the limits of the proposed algorithm, the second exercise involves applying it to real data acquired during tensile tests of metallic samples with different geometries, using digital image correlation (DIC) measurements throughout the test. A key challenge in implementing the developed algorithm with real DIC data is the interpolation of displacements. The FEM model, and consequently the POD basis, refers to displacements at the nodal points of the mesh used to discretize the computational domain, while DIC typically provides a significantly larger number of points with known displacements. In the procedure adopted here, displacements from the DIC data are interpolated to the nodal points of the FEM model. Details of this process are explained in the following section.

3.2.Implementation of developed algorithm for data collected with digital image correlation

3.2.1. Experiments

For verification purposes, a series of tensile tests were conducted on steel samples with varying geometries. All the samples were designed with geometries that would produce a heterogeneous state of stress, and consequently, a non-uniform distribution of deformation. This variation in deformation is expected to negatively impact the correlation of displacements, particularly due to the presence of localized regions of large deformation. In this context, the developed procedure was specifically tested under these more challenging conditions to evaluate its robustness and accuracy. Geometries of the tested samples are depicted in Figure 3. All samples were tested to failure, subjecting them to conditions with significant and localized plastic deformation, prior to formation of cracks. As an example, photos of four different sequences during the testing of

specimen 1 are depicted in Figure 4, clearly evidencing the formation of the crack around the hole.

Figure 3: Samples that were subjected to testing

Figure 4: Four different photos during the experiment corresponding to the increased level of force (from left to right)

3.2.2. Employed equipment for digital image correlation measurements

For measuring displacements the system ARAMIS from company GOM [22] was employed. The system is equipped with 2 cameras, hence three dimensional measurements are possible, even though not used here. For the application tested here, 50mm lens were used, the two cameras were split by 370mm, and the distance from the specimen was 800mm. No out of plane displacements were targeted, hence only photos from one camera were used. With these settings the accuracy of measurements was 0.01mm [22]. For elaboration of photos, system is equipped

with its own software (ARAMIS v6.2.0). However, in the present case, an open source software was used to the purpose, specifically Ncorr [23], as it allowed more flexibility in manipulating data.

Figure 5: Aramis system that is used to take photos during the experiments

3.2.3. Algorithm for reconstruction of missing data

To reconstruct the missing data, a numerical model for all the tested specimens was generated. Since the tests involved large plastic deformations, a classical von Mises plasticity model was used for modeling purposes. The full tensorial description is omitted for brevity (see e.g. [24] for details), and only a compact form of the adopted exponential hardening, based on the traditional Ramberg-Osgood model, is provided. In its original holonomic uniaxial formulation, this reads:

$$\sigma(\varepsilon) = \begin{cases} E \cdot \varepsilon & , \varepsilon < \frac{\sigma_0}{E} \\ \sigma_0^{1-n} \cdot E^n \cdot \varepsilon^n & , \varepsilon \geq \frac{\sigma_0}{E} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where ε represents the total strain, that contains both elastic and plastic part, and σ_0 is a material parameter quantifying the value of stress at the onset of first yielding (i.e., prior to strain hardening). For each specimen a numerical model is build with relatively fine mesh, which is subsequently applied to perform set of simulations in order to construct the POD basis required for the reconstruction. An example of the adopted mesh used to model first specimen is depicted

in Figure 6. The mesh contained 5224 quadrilateral elements, 136 triangular elements, and the overall of 5462 nodes. The other models, not shown here for brevity employed finite element meshes with similar nodes and element numbers.

Figure 6: Adopted finite element mesh for the numerical simulations

To exploit the correlation between displacements, a series of numerical analyses were performed in which three model parameters were varied: the two material parameters (the hardening exponent n and the first yield limit σ_0), and the maximum prescribed displacement at the upper edge of the specimen. Given that the material used for the specimen was a mild steel with no specific treatment, the material properties were selected within the typical range for this material, though with a broader range of parameters, to generate diverse displacement fields. Similarly, the prescribed displacement at the upper edge of the specimen was varied within a slightly wider range compared to the one used in the experiment. A regular grid of points in the parameter space was employed for the simulations, with the following parameter ranges: n from 0 to 0.32 in steps of 0.04; σ_0 from 80 MPa to 170 MPa in steps of 30 MPa; and the upper edge displacement from 2 to 10 mm in steps of 4 mm. This resulted in a total of 108 simulations.

Generated nodal displacements corresponding to the complete set of nodes (i.e., for model of the specimen 1 it resulted in vector of displacement collecting 10924 displacements in two directions of the 5462 nodes). Vectors resulting from 108 simulations were collected in 1092×108 snapshot matrix. By performing a POD analysis on this matrix an optimal new basis is found to which all the original vectors were projected. These vectors are truncated to first 30 dimensions, hence, reducing the dimensionality by more than 3 times. In the new, truncated basis, hence, all the snapshots are represented by 30 amplitudes, which suffice to reconstruct the complete vector of nodal displacements collecting all 10924 displacements (i.e., somewhat different numbers, but with similar range result from numerical models of other specimens).

A sub-region of interest is further selected from which the experimentally measured displacements by DIC are further considered as the only known quantities. Within this region the number of finite element nodes is first identifies, and then the DIC displacements are interpolated to these points. The interpolation is performed in two steps. First, the closest four points that are surrounding the points of interest are identified. Subsequently, finite element shape functions are used to interpolate the displacement to the point of interest.

A sub-region of interest is selected, within which the experimentally measured displacements from DIC are considered the only known quantities. Within this region, the number of finite element nodes is first identified, after which the DIC displacements are interpolated to these points. The interpolation is carried out in two steps. First, the four closest surrounding points, from the collection of points for which DIC measurements are known, to the points of interest are identified. Then, finite element shape functions are used to interpolate the displacements to the point of interest.

For here considered problem for the specimen 1 the region of interest with grid of points where DIC measurements are known are visualized in Figure 7. Displacement from this region are interpolated to the FE nodal points collecting the values within the vector \mathbf{u}_{EXP}^P . The reduced pod basis with only the rows corresponding to the points of the above sub-region are collected in matrix $\bar{\Phi}^{1 \div P}$. The matrix is subsequently used through the equation (8) to compute the counter part of the experimentally measured quantities collected in vector \mathbf{u}_{EXP}^P . It is now goal to find the vector of amplitudes $\bar{\mathbf{a}}_C$ that minimizes the equation (9). For the minimization purposes it was, again, the trust region algorithm as implemented within MATLAB [21] was employed.

Amplitudes that minimize the objective function (9) are further used to reconstruct the complete displacement field. For comparison purposes the complete displacement field from the DIC measurements is used. The same interpolation technique is employed also here to compute the displacement exactly at the location of finite element nodes. The result is visualized in the Figure 8, representing the color coded graph of the difference in displacements expressed in percentage.

Figure 7: DIC grid of points with sub-region from where the displacements are considered as known

The comparison of results evidences and excellent accuracy with maximum error of about 8%, concentrated in the zone of localized plastic deformation as expected. Worth to mention that none of the zones with localized plastic deformation was considered within the known information. Yet, the proposed algorithm managed to reconstruct the measurements also in this zone, with fairly good accuracy.

Figure 8: Difference between DIC measurements and reconstructed measurements by the proposed algorithm

4. Conclusion and future prospect

This paper presents a novel method for reconstructing missing data, specifically designed for measurements obtained through digital image correlation (DIC). The method systematically exploits the correlation between measurements by using proper orthogonal decomposition (POD). The algorithm was tested on both pseudo-experimental data (i.e., computationally generated data) and data collected from real experiments. In the case of computer-generated data, the accuracy of the algorithm was exceptionally high, with the reconstructed displacements being nearly identical to the reference ones. When applied to real experimental data, the accuracy was slightly reduced

but still acceptably high. For cases with no significant localized plastic deformation, the accuracy was less than 1%. However, in regions with localized plastic deformation, the accuracy dropped to around 8%.

The proposed method can be used to reconstruct missing data from DIC measurements in various scenarios, particularly in high-temperature applications where optical difficulties may prevent the displacement from being measured at all points in the test, or when heating devices are obscuring the camera view. It is worth noting that, in the exercise tested, the method was intentionally pushed to its limits, as only about 20% of the region was used to reconstruct displacements for the entire domain. It is expected that the error would decrease significantly when a larger portion of the sample is included.

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